

SUPPRESSION OF RING ARTIFACTS IN RECONSTRUCTED HOLOGRAPHIC IMAGES USING GRAPH SIGNAL PROCESSING

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INTRODUCTION:

Monitoring of pollen concentration is an important task that can help people suffering from pollen allergies. Currently, the most reliable methods for determining concentration and classification of pollen particles require a lot of time and labor. In recent years new devices based on reconstructed holographic images of pollen particles for pollen classification and automatic concentration monitoring have been introduced. Although it is possible to obtain high quality particle images, the acquisition process also introduces various artifacts such as ring artifacts which leads to wrong estimation of the final pollen concentration.

OBJECTIVES:

The aim of this research was to find a method to remove ring artifacts from pollen holographic image reconstructions while preserving important features of particles such as shape and size.

METHOD / DESIGN:

For removing ring artifacts, two methods based on graph signal processing [1] framework were proposed: Taubin smoothing filter (TSF) and optimal graph filter (OGF). Both proposed methods represent translation of basic filter design concepts from classical digital signal processing into a graph domain. The reconstructed holographic images of pollen are modeled as a graph with a 2D lattice structure, where each vertex represents a pixel, and edges only exist between adjacent pixels. While TSF can be treated as a finite impulse response (FIR) filter which is iteratively applied to obtain better denoising results, OGF tends to achieve the same results through only one iteration and it can be considered as an infinite impulse response (IIR) filter.

RESULTS:

We evaluated the proposed methods by using visual inspection of filtered images and regions of interest (ROI) containing only pollen particles. As there are no reference images of pollen particles without artifacts, for objective evaluation it is necessary to use non-reference metric for image quality such as total variation (TV) metric. This metric is often used as a loss-function in the optimization process for image denoising. There are several other ring artifacts removal methods [2] in literature addressing similar problems, but artifacts that are of interest in these cases manifest mainly as ideal circles, while ring artifacts in our data depend on the shape of pollen particles. As a reference method we used Chambolle-Pock (CP) algorithm [3] and results, obtained by calculating TV on ROIs, show that only OGF manages to outperform CP in terms of TV minimization, while results obtained with TSF are slightly worse than with CP. In terms of visual inspection, each method successfully eliminated ring artifacts, while preserving details within pollen particles and their shape. Results are shown in Table 1.

CONCLUSIONS:

Two methods, TSF and OGF, were presented and compared in terms of TV with CP algorithm. Efficiency of both methods was tested on different varieties and shapes of pollen particles and results show that this type of image processing has a potential as a standard preprocessing of holographic image reconstructions.

Figure 1. 100x100 regions around particles (top) and ROI (bottom) in: original (a) and filtered hologram reconstructions using the following algorithms: CP (b), TSF (c) and OGF (d)

TOTAL VARIATION	Average	Standard Deviation	Decrease Factor	
	Original Images		Average	Standard Deviation
Chambolle-Pock	50706	14489	1.21	1.38
Taubin Smoothing Filter	51655	14738	1.19	1.36
Optimal Graph Filter	48910	13479	1.25	1.49

Table 1. Total variation statistics for 19 original and filtered ROI images

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